

Development of Creative Abilities of Primary Class Students in Reading Literacy Lessons

Nabulin Rashid¹

¹ lecturer of the department “Methodology of teaching social sciences and humanities in primary education” Namangan State University (Uzbekistan)

Abstract:

The necessity of developing the creative abilities of primary school students in reading literacy lessons is substantiated. The content of the combination “reading literacy” is revealed. The characteristics of the process of development of creative ability in primary school students using the most effective methodological techniques are presented. A comparative analysis of the concepts “creativity” and “creativity” is proposed. Based on the analysis of scientific and methodological sources, an analysis of the concept of “creative ability” is given.

Keywords: primary stage, system of continuous education, creatively, proactively, creatively, national program for the development of public education, reading literacy, analyze what you read, perception of the problem; search for a solution; the emergence and formulation of hypotheses; hypothesis testing; their modification; finding results, problematic presentation of knowledge; mosaic, verbal development of images of a work, theatrical creative activity. fine art creative activity

Introduction

From the 2022-2023 academic year, in connection with the adoption of the “National Program for the Development of the Public Education System in 2022-2026” [2], the integrated subject “Russian Language and Reading Literacy” was introduced for primary grades, and a corresponding textbook was compiled.

Reading literacy is a person's ability to understand, use, evaluate texts, reflect on them, and engage in reading in order to achieve their goals, expand their knowledge and capabilities, and participate in social life.

Lessons in reading literacy involve the development of creativity, critical thinking, and the involvement of all schoolchildren in creative activities, and not only reading. Depending on their inclinations and inclinations, each junior schoolchild can express himself in creativity in different ways: as a writer, critic, illustrator, reader, actor. Since creative activity presupposes that children have literary and creative skills, a special and targeted system of exercises and tasks is needed, which made it possible to develop the ability to perform creative tasks step by step .

The development of students' creative abilities, starting from primary school age, is one of the most important problems of the lifelong education system. This problem has become particularly relevant in recent decades in connection with large-scale reform of all spheres of life in the country. The changes taking place in the life of society, associated with a change in the economic system, new market relations, orient the education system towards preparing the younger generation, creative, capable of critical thinking, active communication in a rapidly changing, dynamic world. Due to changes in social life, the content and structure of the education system is changing. According to the new educational paradigm, the continuous education system of Uzbekistan is given the priority task of developing the creative activity of students, developing their ability to independently acquire and apply knowledge [1]. In this regard, teachers' attention is currently focused on finding and implementing effective ways to develop students' creative abilities.

Creativity is defined as human activity that creates new material and spiritual values that have novelty and social significance, that is, as a result of creativity, something new is created that did not exist before. The concept of "creativity" can be given a broader definition. Philosophers define creativity as a necessary condition for the development of matter, the formation of its new forms, along with the emergence of which the forms of creativity themselves change [3].

In pedagogy and psychology, the term "creativity" is studied in the context of the concept of "creative activity". Unique creative activity is a specific form of interaction, and the development mechanism acts as a criterion for creativity. Based on this definition, the mechanism for the development of children's creative abilities is the organization of specific forms of interaction between a child and an adult in the process of various types of activities [4].

Methodology for organizing work

Depending on the type of creative activity, we can distinguish 3 groups of methods and techniques that are aimed at stimulating the creative activity of younger schoolchildren and developing creative abilities in literary reading lessons:

- Verbal deployment of images of the work.
- Theatrical creative activity.
- Fine creative activity.

Verbal deployment of images of a work in reading literacy lessons. The purpose of this method is to activate artistic perception, both at the beginning of studying a work and after analysis. The images created by imagination during reading are the result of the reader's creative activity and stimulate verbal creativity. It can be represented by expressing impressions about what you read, recalling a similar incident from your life, inventing a continuation, verbally drawing pictures, or creative retelling.

Creative reading is the basis for the formation of high artistic taste and is driven by curiosity. Methodological techniques that ensure the implementation of the creative reading method: expressive reading, commented reading, creative tasks, posing an educational problem in the lesson.

The issue of developing expressive reading is given great importance, because expressiveness based on thoughtful analysis of the text promotes a deep understanding of the work, episode, phrase, and also contributes to the development of creative reading. The main means of speech expressiveness is intonation. When reading a work of art, intonation arises after comprehension of the text, understanding of the author's intentions and intentions, and a conscious attitude towards the characters, their actions and events. Here are some tasks:

- Convey joy, indignation, pride, sadness in the text;
- Read the passage, conveying fear, surprise, chagrin in your voice;
- Read the sentence with different intonation.

The guys work with pleasure, try different intonation colors and choose for themselves exactly the one that is closer to them in meaning or which is easier to convey. Thus, each student reads the same work with a different feeling, inherent only in his current mood or desire to introduce his comrades to his intonation discovery.

You can hold a competition “Who can read the same word (phrase) with the most shades of intonation” or a game “I won’t let you!” I ask the children to imagine and say: “Give me a toy,” as rain, thunder, or a bird might say. Then answer: “I won’t!”, in the voices of the same characters. Expressive reading by children themselves (by heart or from a book) is a kind of report to the teacher, the class, and themselves about their understanding of the text, its interpretation, practically carried out by the child not only for themselves, but also for others. Such work can be carried out in the form of a reading competition. An effective technique for understanding and finding artistic means is when we do not replace the word, but “turn on” the imagination: “The rain was drumming on the roof” - how do you imagine it?

To develop attention to words, I suggest that children create a crossword puzzle based on the work they read or use ready-made crossword puzzles.

Reception "Mosaic"

The class is divided into pairs and each pair is asked to ask questions about a given passage of text. From the first reading lessons, I use a lot of poetic material: riddles, poems about letters, rhymes, collections of poetic dialogues of varying degrees of complexity, tongue twisters. At primary school age, children show great interest in poetry. But before you start rhyming yourself, you need to be able to read poetry, observe their construction, artistic features, learn to see visual means (comparisons, epithets, metaphors, personifications) that help to understand feelings and experiences. With the help of special exercises, students learn to rhyme words and add rhymed lines.

“One line competition” Given the first line of the poem, we come up with an ending and determine the most successful option.

To develop children's creative abilities, you can use a methodological technique - interpretation of a fairy tale. By interpreting the work, each student has the opportunity to express themselves creatively, acting in a new role.

Here are examples of some tasks of this nature.

Tell the plot of a famous fairy tale on behalf of characters or objects - “participants in events.”

“What happened next?” - complete the plot of the work.

Inclusion of additional characters into the plot of the tale.

Writing fairy tales is one of the effective techniques for developing children's creative abilities and promotes self-expression in younger schoolchildren. Work on creative processing is carried out throughout the study of fairy tales.

1. Solve "fairy tale problems" without changing or minimally changing the plot of the fairy tale:

- What needs to be done so that Ivanushka gets drunk, but doesn't become a little goat?
- How to prevent the Ryaba hen's egg from breaking?
- What does Little Red Riding Hood's grandmother need to do to avoid being eaten by the wolf?

2. "Turning the fairy tale inside out"

This task helps children not only make a parody of a familiar work, but also gives them the opportunity to develop it in any direction.

- Compose a fairy tale using fairy tale words and expressions from this fairy tale, where:

Snow White met seven giants in the forest.

The wolf wanted to eat the kids, but they captured him.

3. Composing a fairy tale at the beginning or at the end.

Children already have the heroes of a fairy tale, the beginning or end of a story, they just need to come up with a continuation. For example, a fairy tale by analogy, a fairy tale and music, a fairy tale by the initial phrase, finishing fairy tales. When composing, you can use humor. It stimulates interest and is an effective way to relieve stress and anxiety.

4. Creating your own original fairy tale. The most difficult type of work. All children need to come up with a name, characters, and plot themselves.

5. "Free speech" technique Imagine that characters from your favorite fairy tales have gathered for a fairy-tale conference on the rights of fairy-tale characters. Each of them comes to the podium and says... (You need to speak on behalf of the fairy-tale hero of your favorite fairy tale). Young schoolchildren gain experience in creative activity not only in the process of reading and analyzing a work of art, but also in the process of creating their own texts. These can be not only fairy tales, but also stories. Starting from the 1st grade, children learn to compose stories by analogy with the work of fiction they read.

Techniques for creating your own texts:

"Write a letter" technique. Students need to write a letter to someone on behalf of the hero of the work; this allows them to put themselves in the place of another, to correlate their thoughts and feelings with their own.

Technique "Writing a fairy tale in a new way." The guys receive pieces of paper on which the characters of their favorite fairy tales are indicated, but words from our modern language are included. Kolobok, grandmother, grandfather, wolf, fox, bear, bicycle, competition. The guys must write a fairy tale using the given words, in a modern way. Time to write a fairy tale is 6 minutes. The group role-plays the story.

Theatrical creative activity in literary reading lessons

Dramatization game. In order to maximize the creative potential of students and develop interest in the literary word, I use the technique of dramatization. During dramatization, each student, creating a unique image of a particular character, shows creativity, because expresses the author's intention in its own way

Working with illustrations. Illustrative work in primary school should begin with the analysis of book illustrations and paintings. Already in literacy lessons, I begin working on illustrations, drawing the children's attention to the facial expressions and poses of the characters depicted in the drawings. Introducing children to reading works based on the illustrative material of books contributes to education, develops the mind, imagination, and aesthetic taste.

Creative dramatization play helps children acquire active and creative team interaction skills. Unlike traditional dramatization games, where roles are learned and scenes are played out according to a specific scenario, creative dramatization games give children scope for creativity and freedom of expression.

Tasks:

1. Portray a girl who has lost her doll. She looks everywhere, but can't find it, and asks the children: "Has anyone seen my bow?"
2. Draw a bunny who is happy when the boy gives him a carrot and says "thank you."
3. Draw a cat and a dog who are angry at each other.
4. Draw a small mouse scared of a cat. She heard a menacing "meow!" and can't find a secluded place to hide. You have turned into the hero of a fairy tale: portray his voice and manners.

Staging the work

When dramatizing, children portray heroes using intonation, facial expressions, posture, and gesture. You can use the following general scheme for staging work:

1. perception of the material to be dramatized;
2. analysis of the work (setting, image of the characters and their actions);
3. setting performance tasks: what needs to be conveyed when acting out a skit?
4. choice of means of expression (how to do this). Samples (studies), analysis. Summing up, its analysis.
5. final show, its analysis.

A more complex form of dramatization is role-based reading, accompanied by an analysis of the emotional state and character traits of the characters, intonation.

One of the important stages of work in a reading literacy lesson is practicing facial expressions, gestures, and movements. The pantomime used here helps to achieve success, in which the child reveals his feelings and understanding of the image, while experiencing only positive emotions

Fine creative activities in reading literacy lessons.

Fine creative activity involves techniques such as drawing an episode that you liked best; drawing a given episode, character, series of drawings; depicting the mood of an episode, work or character; drawing up a hand-drawn filmstrip; appliqué, modeling, making a book layout, viewing and discussing artists' illustrations; drawing up a picture plan.

When working on a work, you can use drawing based on the works you have read. Free associations appear in the drawing. Through color it is easier for a child to convey his attitude towards the characters and the ongoing event. This is how a homemade book is assembled. Illustrating one of the episodes is the emotional response of children, reflecting their understanding of the content of the text and their personal attitude to what they read.

Conclusion

Educational creative activity is considered primarily as an activity that contributes to the development of a whole complex of qualities of a creative personality: mental activity, quick learning, ingenuity and ingenuity, the desire to obtain the knowledge necessary to perform specific practical work, independence in choosing and solving problems, and hard work. The result of such extensive and effective development of the complex of qualities necessary for the development of creative activity should be an independently created (creative) product: a model, layout, poem, toy, etc. Creativity, individuality, and artistry are manifested in at least a minimal deviation from the model.

The goal of developing creative abilities is the general development and formation of the qualities of the creative personality of preschoolers, which can be achieved by creating conditions for a variety of activities to identify and develop children's abilities.

To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

- include children in a variety of activities;
- develop flexible skills that allow children to quickly master new types of work (activities), i.e. transfer of knowledge and skills;
- develop quick wits and quick reactions when solving new and different problems related to practical activities.

Thus, the development of imagination in preschoolers and primary schoolchildren consists of the following features:

- acquisition of arbitrariness, which involves the creation of a plan, its planning and implementation;
- becomes a special activity, turning into fantasy;
- the child masters the techniques and properties of creating images;
- due to the transition to the internal plane, there is no need for visual support for creating images [].

At the same time, only an educational institution can purposefully and on a massive scale contribute to the development of a wide range of children's abilities, giving the child the opportunity to express himself in a wide range of active activities and the most effective way to develop abilities through introducing children to productive creative activities.

References:

1. Resolution No. PF-5712 dated April 29, 2019 "On approval of the Concept for the development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030"
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan UP - 134 "On approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2022 - 2026."
3. Vygotsky L.S. Thinking and speech: collection. – M.: AST; Astrel, 2011. – 637 p.
4. Vygotsky L.S. Thinking and speech: collection. – M.: AST; Astrel, 2011. – 637 p.
5. Poddyakov A.N. Development of research initiative in childhood: Doctoral thesis in psychology. – M.: Faculty of Psychology, Moscow State University, 2001. –350 s.
6. Tamberg Yu.G. Development of a child's creative thinking. – St. Petersburg: Rech, 2011. - 176 p.

7. Ramilevich N. R. Methods of teaching the name of the adjective in russian language lessons in elementary school //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR). – 2020. – Т. 9. – №. 3. – С. 112-115.
8. Nabulin R. R. et al. BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF O'QUVCHILARIGA TA'LIM VA TARBIYA BERISHDA ILG'OR PEDAGOGIK VA AXBOROT-KOMMUNIKATSIYA TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH //Студенческий вестник. – 2019. – №. 24-4. – С. 79-81.
9. Nabulin R. R. РЕЧЕВЫЕ ОШИБКИ УЧАЩИХСЯ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССОВ //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2019. – №. 12. – С. 219-222.
10. Nabulin R. R. Speech errors of primary school students //ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 12 (80). – 2019. – С. 219-222.